

European Public Local Authorities' Network for driving
the Energy Transition

D2.4 - REPORT ON ePLANET CLUSTERING GOVERNANCE (Definition of supporting figures)

First Version

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Executive summary

The ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. This project aims to reframe the current governance model and design and establish a **new clustering governance model** to facilitate the deployment of energy transition projects, creating and improving coordination between different municipalities acting together. This needs to be based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

All these targeted objectives will give the needed support for the energy transition decision-making process and its practical implementation.

Considering the outcomes from the T2.1 and T2.2, this document aims to design a new clustering governance methodology and specifications of the deployment procedures. Moreover, this document will define new figures and the definition of their roles, responsibilities and skills to be provided, depending on the public authority level.

The methodology followed to carry out this deliverable is based on meetings with the pilot site partners and through specific surveys. The three pilot regions, the island of Crete in Greece, the Zlín region in the Czech Republic and the province of Girona in Catalonia, have been consulted to understand how they implement ET projects and what mechanisms they have to achieve.

This document is the draft version, just the first steps in understanding the governance in the three pilot areas and a first glimpse and approach to clustering governance.

This document analyses and explains how each pilot region is currently governed and who makes it happen. The focus is on what we consider is the main tool for the Energy transition, which are the energy plans. Those Plans are performed by the different public authorities, whether they follow or not, the CoM methodology.

This first draft has a submission date for M10; however, a final version needs extra time and dedication to design the governance strategies validating the first identification of figures and a final and definitive governance structure and methodology. This final version has a submission date on month 20, April 30th 2023.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
ABL	Adjusted BaseLine
BL	Base Line
CILMA	Council of local initiative for the environment (in Girona)
CoM	Covenant of Mayors
DDGI	Girona provincial council
DSO	Distributor System Operator (local utility)
EAZK	Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
ECM	Energy Conservation Measures
EA	Energy Agency
ED	Energy data
EP	Energy Plan
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ET	Energy Transition
ETG	Energy Transition Governance
ETM	Energy Transition Measure
ETP	Energy Transition Plan
LA	Local Authorities
LEC	Local Energy Community
MLG	Multilevel governance
PA	Public Authority
PAET	Public Advisor in Energy Transition
RDFC	Regional Development Fund of Crete
REAC	Regional Energy Agency of Crete
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RL	Reporting Line
SEF	State Environmental Fund of the Czech Republic
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan
SECAP	Sustainable Energy Climate and Action Plan

1 Background

Energy transition (ET) deployment initiatives are structured in four main axes: Energy efficiency, savings, Renewables and climate neutrality. The previous deliverable on Governance (D2.1), in which needs and requirements were identified, showed an important interest from all pilot regions on two or more of those previous axes.

Even though ePLANET aims to be a promoter of ET projects by sharing information in a common digital space between different municipalities and other Public Entities (PA) at different levels, digitalisation seems not to be a priority for some local areas.

The development of a clustering governance structure and its methodology needs inputs from all previous tasks under the WP2. Schematically this is represented in the following Figure 1 and explained hereunder.

Figure 1. Overview of the WP2 structure

In Task 2.1, needs and requirements have been identified through surveys conducted on a set of municipalities in the three pilot regions. This task identified as well some use cases, which will help through a deeper analysis to refine the methodology and better adjust figures for working governance.

Task 2.2 has collected current governance structures and tools in not only the three pilot regions but also on all European initiatives, wherever undertaken or ongoing. All this information is very valuable to build up the ePLANET governance proposal.

Task 2.3 on harmonisation of information is another key part of the clustering governance since if the information is not adequately harmonised, it cannot be shared with different interested PA at the same time, and that would create a communication between different municipalities willing to start common ET projects.

Finally, Task 2.5 is another important input for the governance, as the follow-up of the ET projects implemented will be done through different KPIs.

Tasks 2.3 and 2.5 concern to data not only related to energy consumption but to other characteristics such as measures (ETM), energy & climate plans (SECAP), actions and other.

As seen in Figure 1, a draft proposal for ET governance needs to get extra inputs from the three pilot territories' environment; additional information is needed to understand what is their organisation and structure at different geographical and political levels, what initiatives are initiated, ongoing or planned.

1.1 Summary of Task 2.1 (D2.1). Main requirements identified

During Task 2.1, the main requirements and needs from future ePLANET users were identified. Those requirements gave us the information needed to define the features of the platform in order to ensure the future adoption of ePLANET outcomes by its users, mainly Public Authorities at the local level.

At the same time, outcomes from deliverable 2.1 is a value to orientate the approach and design of the governance methodology and the different needed figures for the clustering governance. Ultimately, the objective to achieve is to improve the deployment of energy transition projects at a municipal level.

It is important to remind the main outcomes identified for each pilot region at municipal level as those results serve as a starting point for the definition of an Energy Transition for a clustering governance methodology and figures.

The conclusions reached are the following:

Needs from Municipalities of Zlín region.

- To raise awareness on Energy Transition (ET).
- Increase resources to carry out ET projects
- Increase commitment from municipalities in developing ETP and its governance
- Definition of funding schemes for ET projects deployment

Needs from Municipalities of Crete Island.

- Increase public resources to carry out ET projects.
- Improvements in data gathering
- Definition of funding schemes for ET projects deployment

Needs from Municipalities of Girona province.

- Improvements in data gathering
- Increase public resources to carry out ET projects
- Definition of funding schemes for ET projects

Those results from the D2.1 is a starting point for establishing an ET governance on D2.4.

Deliverable 2.1 identified as well different Use Cases that will allow us to understand its flow processes, a more accurate and thorough design of a governance model and other extra figures.

The defined Use case are:

UC1. Digitalisation of SECAPs. Consists in filling current information of Municipalities Energy Plans under SECAPs Excel files of the CoM.

UC2. Analysis of energy performance of public buildings. It consists in implementing a system to assess and track energy consumption in municipal buildings

UC3. Use of Geo-Tools for promoting energy communities (REC & LEC). It consists in the use of geographically based web visualisations of building energy consumption and renewable energy generation aggregated at municipality level.

UC4. PV potential analysis in public buildings. Consists in setting up a GIS based web environment to show the PV potential and the self-consumption ratio in public buildings.

The following Table 1 summarises the use cases for each pilot region.

Table 1. Use-cases of the pilot regions

UC	Zlín Region	CRETE	Girona province
UC1. Digitalisation of SECAPs	--	- 16 municipalities - Rewrite information from PDF to CoM Excel	- 67 municipalities - Rewrite information from current excels to CoM Excel
UC2. Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock	- In 70 - 80 buildings of 61 municipalities - based on monthly consumption in Excel files	- Implemented in 2 stages: 1 st Stage: 4 municipalities 2 nd stage: 16 municipalities - Based on monthly .xls files of electricity consumption	--
UC3. Use of Geo-Tools for promotion of Energy Communities	- Showcase of the city of Hostětín as a sustainable energy community.	- Implemented in 2 stages: 1 st Stage: 4 municipalities 2 nd stage: 16 municipalities - Data: under Excel format	- Implemented in 2 stages: 1 st Stage: 6 municipalities 2 nd stage: 67 municipalities - Data: under different formats (DATADIS, .CSV ...)
UC4. PV potential analysis in public buildings	- In 70 - 80 rooftops of 61 municipalities - based on LIDAR system and cadastral information of Zlín region.	--	--

These Use Cases will be thoroughly analysed in the final version of this D2.4. The idea is to understand each process through flow diagrams, which will allow us to identify possible new figures and the improvement of the governance by identifying constraints, enablers and resources.

1.2 Summary of Task 2.2 (D2.2). An overview of the current governance networks

Task 2.2 presented an overview of the existing governance networks. The aim was to undertake a desk review, gathering and analysing requirements and best practices from current EU or national governance networks and initiatives from past and/or ongoing projects addressing public authorities' Energy Transition (ET).

The review focused on the following aspects:

- Current legal and policy framework related to energy transition in the pilot partners' regions (national, regional or at a local level).
- Governance status related to energy transition in current EU-wide networks and initiatives (governance structures and tools/methodologies / digital platforms introduced by these networks for coordinating and monitoring energy transition plans and projects).
- Governance status related to energy transition in the pilot partners' regions (existing governance structures and tools/methodologies/digital platforms currently used by public authorities for multilevel governance coordination and monitoring of energy transition plans and projects).
- Best practices on multilevel governance for energy transition (governance structures and /or tools /methodologies /digital platforms), identified from past or ongoing projects of the consortium partners and beyond.

The main conclusions were:

- The review of the legal and policy framework in the pilot territories identified forty-four laws and policy documents/plans relevant to the energy transition. In the three pilot regions, there are also regional-level policies and targets for energy planning and improvement of governance. In the Region of Crete, energy transition actions are also integrated into the broader SE(C)APs developed by Municipalities in the context of the CoM.
- Most Municipalities in the Province of Girona and the Region of Crete are signatories of the CoM and have developed/are developing their SE(C)APs. In the Zlín region, there are no developed SE(C)AP's yet by Municipalities.
- Energy communities and relevant implemented projects are pretty developed in Spain (Province of Girona), less developed in Greece (Region of Crete) and not so developed in the Czech Republic (Zlín Region).
- The review identified ten EU networks, initiatives, and twenty-one past or ongoing EU and national projects, with the participation of one or more of the consortium partners relevant to the ePLANET objectives.

This document found an important potential for improving coordination and multilevel governance for the energy transition in the participating territories. The outcomes of task 2.2 aimed to contribute towards this direction and provide helpful feedback to the subsequent WP2 tasks of the ePLANET project, such as Task T2.4.

1.3 Purpose and organisation of the document

The purpose of the document is to make a first draft proposal of governance for the energy transition in the three pilot regions, the Zlín region, the Crete region and the Girona province. The document is focussed on understanding the structure and organisation of each pilot region and their corresponding countries in relation to the deployment of energy efficiency and renewable energies at a local level, that is at a municipal level but showing how energy transition is coordinated from higher tiers up to the government.

The main idea is that if we can clearly show and understand how Energy Transition is currently deployed in each pilot region, we will be able to design a new methodology and structure for improving the current state, based on identifying current barriers, enablers and resources. This should give a hint for determining the figures for a successful energy transition organisation

This document is organised as follows:

First, a summary of the outcomes of the previous tasks 2.1 (lead by ICAEN) and 2.2 (lead by CRES) are presented since they are the starting point to carry out the objectives of this document, as deliverables 2.1 and 2.2 are the basis on which the governance model has to be founded. This part has already been described in the preceding section.

Next, in the second part, it is analysed the current situation of the administration governance in the pilot partner regions by mapping the structure of the energy transition authorities (vertical and horizontal structures of governance). Moreover, another section of this second part describes an analysis of the current situation of the process flows. The focus is on what we consider the main tool for energy transition deployment: the energy action plans or SECAPS. The overall vision of the current status will allow to define a global vision of the governance and find the outcomes and benefits for the ePLANET users.

Moreover, different scenarios are analysed in each pilot region under their country structure.

Finally, a glimpse at an embryo phase about figures (actors) and methodology is pointed out for the proposed model that will be developed in the next months for the final version to be presented on April 2023.

2 Current situation of the governance in the pilot regions

A first overview of the administrative framework of the three pilot regions is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The administrative framework of the pilot regions

STATE	SPAIN	CZECH REPUBLIC	GREECE
COUNTRY/NATION	CATALONIA	--	--
REGION	--	Zlín Region*	Region of Crete*
PROVINCE / ADMINISTRATIVE UNIT	4 Provinces: Province of Girona* , Province of Barcelona, Province of Tarragon Prvince of Lleida	--	4 Regional Units: Regional Unit of Chania, Regional Unit of Heraklion, Regional Unit of Rethymno and Regional Unit of Lasithi
COUNTY LEVEL	8 in Girona (la Selva, Ripollès, Gironès, Baix Empordà, Alt Empordà, Pla de l'Estany, Garrotxa Cerdanya)	--	--
LANDSCAPE UNIT	20	--	--
MUNICIPALITIES	221	307	24

*The pilot regions of the projects are marked in bold.

As it can be seen, the administrative framework is very different in each pilot region. Catalonia is divided into four levels of subdivision of organisational governance being, one of them the Girona Province (pilot partner region). The Girona province is, therefore, subdivided into eight sub-levels of county levels, which are grouped into landscape units (depending on the climatic conditions and landscape conditions); the total of municipalities of Girona Province is 221. On the other hand, Zlín Region is linked directly to the 307 municipalities without having any subdivision level in terms of governance. Finally, the Region of Crete is divided into 4 Regional Units, in which each regional unit has many municipalities; the total of the municipalities in the Region of Crete is 24.

2.1 Map of energy transition authorities

Regarding the multilevel governance structure, it is seen (Figure 2) that the interaction between PA and stakeholders is realised in horizontal and vertical dimensions. The vertical dimension refers to the interactions between different levels of government, while the horizontal level relates to

interactions within the PA and the stakeholders within the same level¹. Therefore, this wide variety of vertical and horizontal interactions makes innovation on ET policies possible in different parts of the governance system².

Figure 2. Vertical and horizontal governance. [Adapted from ²]

From a legislation point of view, vertical governance is executed between European Commission and different member states. Then all levels under the National level are interrelated, as the same law applies to all levels. Regarding horizontal governance, clustering coordination of projects makes sense mainly between municipalities and between counties or rarely regions or provinces.

An analysis of the division of power and elements of the existing governance framework and mechanisms within the energy transition policies is crucial to better understand the main gaps or/and issues that could be improved. Moreover, stakeholder refers to "the figure or actors" who influence plans and decision-making processes. In this case, the term means stakeholders who are affected by or can affect the ET policies decision-making process by receiving information, consultation, or active participation³.

The MLG governance is different for each pilot region since the geographical particularities to a large extent, and the size and resources of each pilot region are crucial for determining the ET policies framework. Therefore, each pilot region will be deeply analysed and studied.

2.1.1 Girona province

Regarding Girona province, multilevel governance, vertical and horizontal, is seen in Table 3. Desk research was enhanced with a series of interviews for an energy policy analysis of the Girona Province. The goal of these interviews was to provide insights on the MLG approach used for the implementation of the energy transition policies both from the local and regional/national levels.

Table 3. Multilevel governance in Girona Province. Political administration governance

PUBLIC BODIES / INSTITUTIONS		STAKEHOLDERS / PA
EUROPE	European parliament https://www.europarl.europa.eu/portal/en European Commission https://ec.europa.eu/info/index_es	IRENA - International Renewable Energy Agency https://www.irena.org/ IEA - International Energy Agency https://www.iea.org/ IPCC - The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change https://www.ipcc.ch/
STATE	The Ministry for the ecological transition and demographic challenge https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/	IDAE - Institute for Diversification and Saving of Energy https://www.idae.es/home
COUNTRY / NATION	Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda DGE - General Directorate of Energy http://sac.gencat.cat/sacgencat/AppJava/or ganisme_fitxa.jsp?cap=false&codi=21709	ICAEN - Catalan energy institute https://icaen.gencat.cat
REGION	--	--
PROVINCIAL	Diputació de Girona - DDGI (Council of Girona) https://www.ddgi.cat/web/	Specialized municipal technician ET External consultancies
	20 supramunicipal (landscape unit)	
COUNTY	8 County council	Energy transition office (3) Energy agencies (when not ETO)
LOCAL	Municipality	Specialised municipal technician ET Local consultant companies

Regarding the European level (all pilot regions are regions or nations members of the EU), it should be worth mentioning that there are four main decision-making institutions⁴, which lead the EU's administration. These institutions provide the EU with policy direction and play different roles in the law-making process:

- the European Parliament
- the European Council

- the Council of the European Union
- the European Commission

However, the European Commission is the EU's main executive body. It uses its 'right of initiative' to propose new laws scrutinising and adopted by the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Then, these laws or directives are transposed to each EU member state⁵.

The administrative structure of the Girona Province consists of seen levels of subdivision, each with corresponding administrative organisations (see Table 3); each public body has one or more stakeholders, which influence the decision-making processes. As mentioned above, the structure is not always hierarchical since the relationship depends on any case.

The highest share of power belongs to the national level, i.e. The Ministry for the ecological transition and demographic challenge, including legislative and executive power in matters such as energy transition. However, Catalonia has certain legislative and executive competencies in agreement with article 133 of the Spanish constitution. The counties and the municipalities have no legislative power, and they stand solely as an administrative body but can promote municipal by-laws.

2.1.2 Zlín Region

Regarding the Zlín region, multilevel governance, vertical and horizontal, is seen in Table 4. Desk research was enhanced with a series of interviews as in the previous partner pilot region. These interviews aimed to provide significant insights on the MLG approach used for implementing the energy transition policies both from the local and regional/national levels.

Table 4. Multilevel governance in the Zlín region. Political governance

PUBLIC BODIES / INSTITUTIONS		STAKEHOLDERS / PA
EUROPE	European parliament https://www.europarl.europa.eu/portal/en European Commission https://ec.europa.eu/info/index_es	IRENA - International Renewable Energy Agency https://www.irena.org/ IEA - International Energy Agency https://www.iea.org/ IPCC - The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change https://www.ipcc.ch/
STATE	Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic https://www.mzp.cz/en	State Environmental Fund of the Czech Republic https://www.sfzp.cz/en/
COUNTRY / NATION	--	--

REGION	Zlín Region https://www.kr-zlinsky.cz/en/	Energy agency of the Zlín Region https://www.eazk.cz/en/
PROVINCIAL	--	--
COUNTY	--	--
LOCAL	Municipality	Energy agency of the Zlín Region https://www.eazk.cz/en/ Specialised municipal technicians - (only in major towns) Veronica https://www.veronica.cz/

In the Czech Republic, there is not any national energy agency. However, the State Environmental Fund of the Czech Republic (SEF), a major state institution of the environmental sector, has contributed to investments to protect and improve the environment.

Nevertheless, in the case of the Zlín region, the Energy agency of the Zlín Region (EAZK) is the facilitating body for both the Zlín Region and the municipalities of the Zlín Region. It is worth mentioning that there is no relation between regional energy agencies to the national level regarding the subordination point of view.

Furthermore, it appears at the local level the NGO Consultancy Veronica, which sometimes acts as an energy agency. Finally, there are specialised municipal technicians rarely and only in major towns.

2.1.3 Crete

Multilevel governance is studied in the Crete region. Desk research was enhanced with a series of interviews for an energy policy analysis with the pilot partner. A summary of the public bodies/institutions concerning the MLG of the Region of Crete is summarised in Table 5.

Table 5. Multilevel governance in Region of Crete. Political governance.

PUBLIC BODIES		STAKEHOLDERS / PA
EUROPE	European parliament https://www.europarl.europa.eu/portal/en European Commission https://ec.europa.eu/info/index_es	IRENA - International Renewable Energy Agency https://www.irena.org/ IEA - International Energy Agency https://www.iea.org/ IPCC - The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change https://www.ipcc.ch/
STATE	Ministry of Environment & Energy https://ypen.gov.gr/	Center For Renewable Energy Sources (CRES) http://www.cres.gr Energy managers of Central government buildings
COUNTRY / NATION	--	--
REGION	Region of Crete https://www.crete.gov.gr/en/	Regional Development Fund of Crete (RDFC) - Regional Energy Agency (REAC) https://www.pta.gr/ Technical Region personnel Energy managers of Regional buildings
PROVINCIAL	4 Regional Units (all under the same administration: Region of Crete) Regional Unit of Chania Regional Unit of Heraklion Regional Unit of Rethymno	Regional Unit personnel
COUNTY	--	--
LOCAL	Municipality	Specialised municipal technicians Energy managers

		Municipality CoM contact persons External consultant
--	--	---

The Ministry of Environment & Energy is the government authority in Greece for all issues related to energy policy and energy transition at the national level. CRES is the Greek national entity for promoting renewable energy sources, rational use of energy and energy conservation. CRES (National CoM coordinator) also has an institutional role in providing technical support to local/regional authorities to prepare energy efficiency plans and actions and support the Ministry of Environment & Energy in implementing energy efficiency policy. Moreover, there is another figure: energy managers of Central government buildings (which are personnel of each relevant Government authority owning public buildings e.g. Ministries etc.).

At the regional level, within the framework of implementing regional energy policy, the Region of Crete founded its Regional Energy Agency (REAC), which is operative via the Regional Development Fund of Crete (Regional CoM coordinator).

At a municipal level, there are four different stakeholders/figures involved; municipality personnel (Technical Services Department, Financial Department, Development Department etc.). Energy managers of Municipal buildings (personnel of the Municipality). Municipality CoM contact persons (Mayors are the formal signatories, and there are also designated CoM contact persons - typically a public officer of the planning department, technical department, development department etc.). A specialist external consultant, in many cases, supports the Municipality in developing and monitoring its action plan.

2.2 Current situation of governance of SECAPS

This section describes the current initiatives in the three pilot regions conducted by local and regional authorities in order to organise a strategy to deploy Energy Transition activities.

The main tool used to deploy Energy Transition is an energy action plan, whether a SEAP, SECAP or any other kind of energy plan. The energy Plan (EP) can be developed following the guidance from European Commission through the CoM, or recommendations from local, regional or national initiatives.

The first starting task is to make the drafting of the Energy Plan at the municipal level. To undertake this task, it is usually done through a tendering process to select a specialised company. Currently, the draft of an Energy Plan is not following the CoM format, but subsequently, after the digitalisation process, the final SECAP is under the CoM format.

To understand governance, besides the description of the current process flows, it is necessary to display how each pilot region is organised in geographical and administrative terms. Based on this organisation and structure, a Governance model and different figures will be proposed to achieve an effective ET governance in each Pilot region and for any European Country.

2.2.1 Girona province

• Drafting of SECAPS

The following Figure 3 is the process flow chart in the case of the province of Girona to make a SECAP.

Figure 3. Process flow chart of SECAPS in Girona province

This flow diagram points out the main actions performed during the process of drafting an Energy Action Plan since the municipality is aware to have an ET Plan.

The inception of this process is anyway in the policy makers of each municipality and the law requiring that each municipality has to have an energy action plan and its implementation in a determined timeframe period. This is being reported to all municipalities by the provincial council.

In the pilot of the province of Girona, the province council, DDGI, is the entity which makes the leadership and supports all municipalities in the different actions for Energy Transition deployment.

Municipalities with more than 20.000 inhabitants can receive advice from DDGI, but the tasks for getting a SECAP have to be done by themselves, as their size justifies a structure with enough technical and legal resources to prepare and award a consulting company for developing the SECAP.

For municipalities of less than 20.000 inhabitants, this process is conducted by the DDGI. Some municipalities have technicians, but economic and legal resources are not sufficient to undertake ET initiatives.

In the graphic of Figure 3, there are three key stakeholders identified as "FIG". In fact, these are figures already existing or to be defined. For this diagram, the identified figures are the follows:

- Figure (1). Mayor or technician of the municipality establishing a communication relationship with the provincial council.
- Figure (2). Provincial Council Team that usually conducts tendering processes.
- Figure (3). Team or technicians from the municipality with expertise in the tendering process.

• Deployment of SECAPS

The implementation of actions determined in SECAPs is under the sole responsibility of each municipality (Figure 4). The energy plan should specify the timeframe period in which actions will be implemented.

Figure 4. Deployment of the SECAPS in the Girona province

As this figure shows, if the municipality has resources (more than 20.000 inhabitants), municipal technicians, "FIG₁", will select the set of measures to implement, and an internal municipal team will conduct the tendering process to award a company (usually an ESCo) for the implementation of the ETM.

In case, the municipality has no resources (less than 20.000 inhabitants), then the municipality will establish contact to the Provincial Council. The person establishing this contact can be the Mayor or a municipal alderman. The provincial council will conduct the selection of the measures to implement and the tender for its implementation.

The responsible "FIG₂" for selecting the ETM and conducting the tendering process are persons of the provincial council in charge of these supporting tasks.

- **Monitoring and control**

Once ETM have been implemented, a follow-up to test results has to be done in order to check if targets are achieved (Figure 5).

This task is normally outsourced to the company that has implemented the measures, as a part of their service maintenance. In certain cases, it can be done as well by municipal technicians

Figure 5. Flow chart of the monitoring of the SECAPS once implemented

This flow-chart starts at implemented measures from the SECAP (namely ECM in public buildings), Renewable energy systems or Energy communities of different types.

As it is important to know the impact and effectivity of the measures implemented, somebody (FIG1) has to assign the resources for the follow-up of measures. This assigned technician or team (FIG2) is who will track results, which will be compared, to the targets of the Energy Plan. This task, might involve the awarded company and municipal or provincial council technicians.

2.2.2 Zlín Region

Czech Republic is not under the CoM Standards concerning the drafting of Energy Action Plans. This is not an obstacle for the deployment of energy transition measures. Clustering governance will be different depending on each geographical regions and its own specific organisation and structure.

- **Drafting of Energy Action Plans**

The process flow for the drafting of energy action plans in the municipalities of the Zlín Region follows the following diagram.

Figure 6. Process flow chart of SECAPS in Zlín region

EAZK is the regional energy agency that guides and supports municipalities in getting their energy action plans. As seen in the preceding scheme, energy plans are developed by external consulting companies.

Energy plans are definitely not under the umbrella of the CoM. This should not be a barrier for the implementation of ETM neither for the development of a clustering governance model that has to foster ET implementation.

Furthermore, Energy Agency of the Zlín Region (EAZK) is implementing and monitoring the Energy Action Plan and the Energy Efficiency Financing Plan of the Zlín Region for the period 2020 - 2024. The structure of this plan reflects the need of the Zlín Region energy policy, and the Regional Energy Concept was one of the starting points for the development of this plan. The plan was drafted by EAZK with the help of stakeholders forums, workshops and long years' experience in the regional energy field. This plan was approved by the Assembly of the Zlín Region, is implemented by EAZK and is monitored on yearly basis. The implementation is reported on yearly basis to the Management Board of EAZK which consists of 6 members nominated, approved and appointed by the Zlín Region Assembly.

Municipalities normally do not develop structured energy action plans. The measures related to the Energy Transition they take are based on their own various priorities, EAZK is a facilitator for them in systematic approach and access to the national funds promoting ET measures. The approach is for each municipality individual and it is not possible to describe a universal workflow. Many municipalities are assisted in their ET measures by EAZK, some of them use services of external energy companies and some of them are trying individually without any external help. EAZK has helped to a couple of municipalities to develop their own Energy Action Plan, however, such plans are quite simple, tailored on each municipality needs. They are eventually approved by municipal assemblies and reported to them on regular basis.

- **Deployment of Energy Action Plans**

The implementation of energy measures in the Zlin region depend on the availability of resources, in the municipality and in the regional energy agency.

First are the resources to start the process for the awarding a company through a tendering process. After the needed economic resources for the implementation of measures.

Figure 7. Deployment of the SECAPS in the Zlin Region

In this scheme, there are two figures to define: one is from the municipality and the other one from EAZK.

- **Monitoring and control**

To monitor and control the impact of the ETM, follows a common scheme for its follow-up

Figure 8. Flow chart of the monitoring of the SECAPS once implemented

EAZK agency assigns a figure, which will do the tracking of the targets established in the Energy Action Plan to check and test results and savings.

2.2.3 Crete

- **Drafting of SECAPS**

The elaboration of the energy action plans in the Crete region follows the following diagram.

Figure 9. Process flow chart of SECAPS in Crete Region

In Greece and in Crete, the Municipality is the public body that must have the interest in having an Energy Plan (EP). Not all EP necessarily are SECAPS. In fact, different kinds of energy plans are elaborated at the national level.

Different energy agencies, as CRES at a national level and RDFC and REAC at regional level, act as advisors for giving support on the drafting of EP, but in the 99% of cases, the elaboration of the energy plans are externalised to an specialised consulting company, even if the municipality has own capable resources for this task.

From this flow diagram two figures appear. One at the energy agency side, as a public advisor to give guidance to the municipalities. The other at the municipality side, as the responsible for initiating and following all process in the development of the energy plan which is outsourced to an specialised consulting company through a tendering process.

- **Deployment of SECAPS**

The implementation of energy transition measures identified in the Energy Plans are only implemented if the municipality has subsidies from European Funding programs as Next Generation Funds or from national or regional programs.

Figure 10. Deployment of the SECAPS in the Crete Region

The identified figure in this process diagram is a person or a team from the municipality in charge for deployment of energy strategies. Some municipalities have various technicians.

- **Monitoring and control**

The Crete case for tracking the response and the impact of the ETM implemented follows the same scheme as in the other pilot regions. The point is to identify and define the figure having the accountability for the monitoring and control.

Figure 11. Flow chart of the monitoring of the SECAPS once implemented

2.3 Global vision of governance. Outcomes and benefits for ePLANET Users

The governance for the implementation of energy transition initiatives in the different European countries can be considered that begin at the European level with the legislation that applies to all countries for the implementation of renewables and energy efficiency projects.

Besides, at the European level, there are different organisations and authorities that support the networking and energy policies

The following diagram is represented for the three pilot regions considered in this project, other 3 levels under the European level: the country or national level, that as seen is equivalent to the state level, the regional or provincial level and the local or municipal level in which ET actions have to be deployed. In this scheme are represented the entities having a key role on energy transition in each pilot region.

The clustering governance can be considered as a multilevel governance model that flows vertically and horizontally. In fact, the horizontal governance at a local level is what this ePLANET initiative is trying to promote to foster projects between different municipalities at the same time.

Figure 12. Summary of the three pilot regions' current governance

Independently of the structure of each country, the global pattern that follows the governance (MLG) is represented in the following graphic (Figure 13).

Figure 13. The analytical framework of an institutional arrangement. [Adapted from 6]

- **Global diagram**

The following diagram (Figure 14) is a global vision that justifies the ePLANET platform as a tool for evaluating savings achieved after the implementation of the energy transition measures

Figure 14. Global vision of the ePLANET platform benefits

It is important to remark that the savings are the difference between the collected data after measures are implemented (reporting line data) and the adjusted baseline data, which is the parametrisation of the behaviour of the facility or building under the energy transition process.

ePLANET platform, besides of facilitating the coordination and collaboration between different users, must have the capacity and ability for calculating savings in terms of energy and CO₂ emissions.

3 Analysis of the different scenarios

There are different scenarios for the deployment of the energy transition in the three different pilot regions as they geographically have different structure and organisation. By scenarios, we refer to the geographical structure from the local/regional level to the national level.

Based on the geographical organisation, is how deployment structure and methodology will be designed. The following Table 6, summarises the main characteristic of each pilot region and the country they belong to.

Table 6. Overview of the three pilot regions.

Country/Nation	Czech Republic	Greece	Catalonia
Surface (Km ²)	78.871	131.957	32.108
Population	10.700.000	10.720.000	7.566.000
# of regions/provinces	14	13	4
# of municipalities	6.258	325	947
Pilot	Zlín Region	Crete Region	Girona province
Surface (Km ²)	3.964	8.336	5.910
Population	580.119	682.928	781.218
# of municipalities	307	24	221

The number of figures to define in this project will depend on each region or country's structure and size. If we want a successful solution for the deployment of ET projects in order to reach all municipalities, specific and adapted figures have to be determined in each pilot region, mainly in relation to the population and number of municipalities.

3.1 Catalan Scenario. Girona Pilot

The Catalan scenario is based on four different tiers for the deployment of the ET. It consists in a pyramidal structure where ICAEN is at the higher level and who will lead the ET process.

Until now, provincial councils have been the only public authorities working with municipalities.

Nowadays, ICAEN is taken the role of promoting and foster ET deployment through a new strategy called 'PLATER'. This is a strategic and sectorial Plan for the deployment of renewable energies in Catalonia.

Under this strategic Plan, ICAEN will promote a third county level. Up to now, each provincial council was giving support to all municipalities under their province. This was not effective enough, as there are too many municipalities per province to have a good governance.

This strategic Plan is considering a new concept as an Energy Transition Office (ETO). Each county will have one ETO in what currently is the County Council.

As can be seen, for the Girona's pilot, it's easier to govern 218 municipalities from 8 public offices (around 28 municipalities per ETO) than from one unique office.

Figure 15. Girona Province Scenario

Briefly, the strategy to start with this new focus, is giving direct support to all 42 ETOs from ICAEN, by funding each ETO to contract one technician, which objectives will be, the deployment of SECAPs.

This plan is currently considering funding this new technical structure for two years.

3.2 Czech Republic Scenario. Zlín Region Pilot

The Czechian scenario is based mainly on two tiers of governance since there is no national energy agency to make a global country policy for the deployment of the energy transition.

The governance for the ET deployment starts at the regional level, which is done by each regional energy agency directly in the municipalities.

The following figure graphically exposes the scenario of governance in the Czech Republic.

Figure 16. Zlin Region Scenario

3.3 Greek Scenario. Crete Region Pilot

The Greek scenario is in between the two preceding scenarios. It can work under a pyramidal structure or from the regional level. Each municipality choose their option. Both national and regional levels can make the governance over the municipalities.

Figure 17. Crete Region Scenario

In case the governance is conducted from the regional level, it can be more operable at least for the Crete pilot, since there is not a huge quantity of municipalities per each regional public authority.

Resources for a successful deployment of ET strategy have to be analysed based on the number of municipalities and populations.

4 Definition and proposal of figures and methodology for each Pilot Region

This draft document version has identified some figures through the analysis of the current governance situation in the above section 2. Figures will be developed in the next final version of this deliverable which will be performed during the next 10 months.

4.1 Figures in Girona Province

The figures for this pilot at local and Catalan country levels have been defined at an embryo stage.

The idea is to provide technical resources at county level, in each county council office re-defined as energy transition offices (ETO)

Those figures will work as facilitators supporting energy transition actions at the local level for the deployment of ETM.

The requirements each defined figure will be developed in the final version of this document as their needed capacity buildings.

4.2 Figures for governance in the Zlín regions

A proposal will be determined, defined and described based on what has been analysed in the above section 2 of this document.

4.3 Figures for governance in the Crete region

To be defined based on previous descriptions of section 2.

5 Conclusions

The overall conclusions will be studied in the final version in the final deliverable in M20.

6 Bibliography

1. Dobravec, V., Matak, N., Sakulin, C. & Krajačić, G. Multilevel governance energy planning and policy: a view on local energy initiatives. *Energy, Sustainability and Society* **11**, (2021).
2. Jänicke, M. Horizontal and vertical reinforcement in global climate governance. *Energies (Basel)* **8**, 5782-5799 (2015).
3. Jetoo, S. Stakeholder engagement for inclusive climate governance: The case of the City of Turku. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* **11**, (2019).
4. Commission, E. *Europe in 12 lessons*. doi:10.2775/69291.
5. Tsebelis, G. & Garrett, G. The Institutional Foundations of Intergovernmentalism and Supranationalism in the European. *International Organization* **55**, 357-390 (2001).
6. Koelman, M., Hartmann, T. & Spit, T. J. M. When tensions become conflicts: wind turbine policy implementation and development in the Netherlands. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management* **65**, 375-397 (2022).

7 Annex

Template of table 2

STATE	SPAIN	CZECH REPUBLIC	GREECE
COUNTRY/NATION			
REGION			
PROVINCE / ADMINISTRATIVE UNIT			
COUNTY LEVEL			
LANDSCAPE UNIT			
MUNICIPALITIES			

Template of table 3-4-5

PUBLIC BODIES / INSTITUTIONS		STAKEHOLDERS / PA
EUROPE	<p>European parliament https://www.europarl.europa.eu/portal/en</p> <p>European Commission https://ec.europa.eu/info/index_es</p>	<p>IRENA - International Renewable Energy Agency https://www.irena.org/</p> <p>IEA - International Energy Agency https://www.iea.org/</p> <p>IPCC - The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change https://www.ipcc.ch/</p>
STATE		
COUNTRY / NATION		
REGION		
PROVINCIAL		
COUNTY		
LOCAL		

The geographical organisation of the three pilot regions. Detailed scheme.

Catalonian structure.

Land	Province	Provincial Council	County	County Council (County Capital)	number of municipalities	population	Average Popul per Municipality	County #	Total pop	# city halls
CATALONIA. Energy Agency @ country level: ICAEN	Bcn	DIBA	Anoia	Igualada	33	124.112	3.761	1		
			Alt Penedès	Vilafranca del P.	27	110.172	4.080	2		
			Bages	Manresa	30	180.962	6.032	3		
			Berguedà	Berga	31	40.004	1.290	4		
			Osona	Vic	50	164.077	3.282	5		
			Moianès	Moià	10	14.243	1.424	6		
			Garraf	Vilanova i la Geltrú	6	154.264	25.711	7		
			Baix Llobregat	S. Feliu de Llobregat	30	833.312	27.777	8		
			Barcelonès	Barcelona	5	2.280.967	456.193	9		
			Vallès Occidental	Sabadell i Terrassa	23	937.422	40.757	10		
			Vallès Oriental	Granollers	39	415.789	10.661	11		
			Maresme	Mataró	30	459.625	15.321	12	5.714.949	314
	Girona	DDGI	Alt Empordà	Figueres	68	143.762	2.114	13		
			Baix Empordà	La Bisbal d'Emp.	36	137.268	3.813	14		
			Garrotxa	Olot	21	59.163	2.817	15		
			Ripollès	Ripoll	19	25.449	1.339	16		
			Cerdanya	Puigcerdà	10	10.230	1.023	17		
			Pla de l'Estany	Banyoles	11	32.876	2.989	18		
			Gironès	Girona	27	196.768	7.288	19		
			Selva	Sta. Coloma d Farnés	26	175.702	6.758	20	781.218	218
	Lleida	DILLEI	Aran	Vielha	9	10.372	1.152	21		
			Alta Ribagorça	Pont de Suert	3	3.945	1.315	22		
			Alt Urgell	La Seu d'Urgell	19	20.453	1.076	23		
			Cerdanya (occi)	Puigcerdà	7	9.000	1.286	24		
			Pallars Jussà	Tremp	14	13.170	941	25		
			Pallars Sobirà	Sort	15	7.101	473	26		
			Noguera	Balaguer	30	39.169	1.306	27		
			Solsonès	Solsona	15	13.600	907	28		
			Segarra	Cervera	21	23.412	1.115	29		
			Pla d'Urgell	Mollerusa	16	36.769	2.298	30		
			Urgell	Tàrrrega	20	37.276	1.864	31		
			Segrià	Lleida	38	211.609	5.569	32		
			Garrigues	Borgues Blanques	24	19.010	792	33	444.886	231
	Tarragona	DITA	Alt Camp	Valls	23	45.045	1.958	34		
			Baix Camp	Reus	28	195.098	6.968	35		
			Baix Penedès	El Vendrell	14	110.439	7.889	36		
			Conca de Barberà	Montblanc	22	20.104	914	37		
			Priorat	Falset	23	9.239	402	38		
			Baix Ebre	Tortosa	14	78.721	5.623	39		
			Ribera d'Ebre	Móra d'Ebre	14	21.864	1.562	40		
			Terra Alta	Gandesa	12	11.401	950	41		
			Montsià	Amposta	12	68.397	5.700	42		
			Tarragonès	Tarragona	22	262.001	11.909	43	822.309	184
								7.763.362	947	

Czech Republic structure

Land	Regions (NUTS 3 level)	Region Capital / Administrative centre	Regional councils	Regional Energy Agencies	number of municipalities	population	Average Popul per Municipality
Czech Republic. NO Energy Agency @ country level.	Prague (capital city)	Prague	Prague City Council	n/a	1	1.335.084	1.335.084
	Central Bohemian Region	Prague	Central Bohemian Regional Council	n/a	1144	1.397.997	1.222
	South Bohemian Region	České Budějovice	South Bohemian Regional Council	n/a	624	643.551	1.031
	Plzeň Region	Plzeň	Council of the Plzeň Region	n/a	501	591.041	1.180
	Karlovy Vary Region	Karlovy Vary	Council of the Karlovy Vary Region	n/a	134	293.311	2.189
	Ústí nad Labem Region	Ústí nad Labem	Council of the Ústí nad Labem Region	n/a	354	817.004	2.308
	Liberec Region	Liberec	Liberec Regional Council	n/a	215	442.476	2.058
	Hradec Králové Region	Hradec Králové	Council of the Hradec Králové Region	n/a	448	550.803	1.229
	Pardubice Region	Pardubice	Council of the Pardubice Region	n/a	451	522.856	1.159
	Olomouc Region	Olomouc	Council of the Olomouc Region	n/a	402	630.522	1.568
	Moravian-Silesian Region	Ostrava	Moravian-Silesian Regional Council	Moravian-Silesian Energy Centre	300	1.192.834	3.976
	South Moravian Region	Brno	South Moravian Regional Council	CEJIZA, s.r.o.	673	1.195.372	1.776
	Vysočina Region	Jihlava	Vysočina Regional Council	Energy Agency of Vysočina	704	508.852	723
Zlín Region	Zlín	Council of the Zlín Region	Energy Agency of the Zlín Region	307	580.119	1.890	
					6.258	10.701.822	

Crete Region structure

Region	Regional councils	Administrative units (subregions)	Municipalities Names	population	number of municipalities	Region Population	Average population
Crete	1	Chania	Apokoronou	15.660	7	171.822	24.546
			Kantanou-Selinou	5.645			
			Kissamou	11.009			
			Chanion	116.154			
			Platania	20.972			
			Sfakion	2.224			
			Gavdou (island)	158			
		Rethymo	Rethymno	62.886	5	97.059	19.412
			Mylopotamou	17.464			
			Amariou	5.843			
			Agiou Vasiliou	8.484			
			Anogeion	2.382			
		Heraklio	Heraklion	175.113	8	338.052	42.257
			Maleviziou	29.062			
			Archanon-Asterousion	16.780			
			Festou	24.572			
			Gortynas	15.680			
			Hersonissou	53.337			
			Minoa Pediadas	17.829			
			Viannou	5.679			
Lassithi	Agiou Nikolaou	28.033	4	75.995	18.999		
	Siteias	18.155					
	Ierapetras	27.450					
	Oropediou	2.357					

